

**IRON DEFICIENCY CONDITIONS IN CARDIOVASCULAR
DISEASES: IMPACT ON THE PROGNOSIS AND FEATURES OF
CORRECTION**

G. I. Akhmedova

Bukhara State Medical Institute. Bukhara, Uzbekistan

axmedovagulmira36@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1716-8128>

Annotation: The article discusses the problem of comorbidity of iron deficiency states and cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Iron deficiency conditions (latent iron deficiency and iron deficiency anemia) significantly increase the risk of developing and progressing CVD. A number of studies have found that regardless of the presence or absence of anemia, iron deficiency leads to the development of cardiovascular complications, a decrease in the quality of life and an increase in mortality in patients with CVD. Currently, the most studied is the effect of iron deficiency conditions on the prognosis of patients with chronic heart failure (CHF). The article discusses the etiology and pathogenesis of the development of iron deficiency in CHF, the mechanisms of its adverse effect on the quality of life, functional status and prognosis of patients' life. The article presents an analysis of clinical studies on the treatment of iron deficiency conditions in CHF and excerpts from current clinical recommendations. We also present data indicating the possible contribution of basic CHF therapy to the correction of anemia and iron deficiency. The article discusses the impact of iron deficiency conditions on the course and prognosis of life in atrial fibrillation (AF) and coronary heart disease (CHD). The negative contribution of iron deficiency states to the development of CVD exacerbations, an increase in the number of hospitalizations, and an increased risk of death in these categories of patients is emphasized. Despite the known negative impact of iron deficiency conditions on the functional status and

prognosis of patients with CVD, there is still insufficient data on the effectiveness and safety of iron deficiency correction in patients with CVD.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, iron deficiency, chronic heart failure, ischemic heart disease, prognosis

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) occupy leading positions worldwide both in terms of prevalence and in the structure of mortality. The prevalence of CVD in the population increases with increasing age and in Uzbekistan and is more than 50% among the population over 70 years of age [1][2]. Factors that aggravate the course of CVD include iron-deficient conditions (latent iron deficiency and iron-deficient anemia), the occurrence of which also increases with age. Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is an independent predictor of cardiovascular diseases and adverse outcomes[1]. In a population-based ARIC-study (Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities), which followed 13,883 patients without CVD for more than 6 years, it was shown that patients with reduced hemoglobin levels had an almost 1.5-fold higher risk of developing CVD, regardless of all other CVD risk factors[2]. A number of studies have found that regardless of the presence or absence of anemia, iron deficiency leads to the development of cardiovascular complications, a decrease in the quality of life and an increase in mortality in patients with CVD [3][4]. At the same time, the correction of iron deficiency and IDA in CVD has features that should be taken into account in clinical practice. It should also be noted that the correction of iron deficiency in recent years has been studied in detail in chronic heart failure (CHF), but remains insufficiently covered in diseases such as coronary heart disease (CHD), atrial fibrillation (AF) [5].

IRON DEFICIENCY AND HEART FAILURE

Iron deficiency conditions are often found in heart failure (HF) and are associated with poor prognosis in both chronic heart failure (CHF) and acute HF[6]. An independent negative effect of anemia on the risk of hospitalization and death among patients with HF has been shown in many studies[6][7]. It was found that anemia

significantly worsens the prognosis of patients with HF and low left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF): all-cause mortality was 48% higher, death or hospitalization was 28% higher, and hospitalization due to HF was 42% higher in patients with anemia compared to patients without anemia [7]. Anemia has a pronounced negative impact on the prognosis of life in patients with acute decompensated HF. In one study that analyzed the effect of anemia on the prognosis of life in patients with acute HF at follow-up for a year, after adjusting for age, severity of HF, systolic and diastolic blood pressure and creatinine levels, it was shown that the risk of death of patients with anemia was 50% higher compared to the risk in patients with severe heart failure. those who did not have anemia [8].

Iron deficiency is the most important cause of anemia in patients with HF, although other causes that may include chronic inflammatory diseases and chronic kidney disease (CKD) should also be investigated [6]. Iron deficiency conditions in HF may be associated with malignancies of the gastrointestinal tract, which were reported in approximately 10% of patients with HF who underwent endoscopic examination in a large study [9]. Iron deficiency can also develop during the patient's life due to physiological (pregnancy, lactation, menstrual cycle features, and old age) and pathological causes (digestive disorders, vegetarianism, malnutrition, and helminthic infestations), which later, when CHF is added, also negatively affects the patient's life prognosis [6]. It is necessary to take into account the increased risk of iron deficiency in patients with HF when taking antiplatelet drugs, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, anticoagulants, proton pump inhibitors, and antacids [10].

Iron deficiency should be considered as an independent clinically significant concomitant condition that occurs independently of the presence or absence of anemia in approximately half of patients with stable CHF [11] and up to 83% of cases in acute decompensated HF, often without the presence of anemia [12]. Iron deficiency has a more pronounced negative impact on the prognosis of patients than anemia without iron deficiency [10]. Iron deficiency in patients with HF is associated with low exercise tolerance, reduced quality of life, and increased risk of hospitalization and death [10].

Iron deficiency in acute HF is likely to have an even greater negative impact on the prognosis. The study showed that the risk of death of patients with acute HF within a year after discharge from the hospital correlated with the presence of iron deficiency (defined as low levels of hepcidin and high levels of soluble transferrin receptor (rRTp) and was 41% for patients with iron deficiency versus 0% for patients without iron deficiency, which was shown regardless of the presence of anemia [4]. It is known that iron deficiency is a common occurrence in acute decompensated HF and correlates with a pronounced effect on the frequency of repeated hospitalizations. According to the results of the study, patients with absolute iron deficiency were hospitalized 72% more often than patients without iron deficiency [13]. Patients with an episode of acute decompensated HF and concomitant iron deficiency represent a high-risk target population in which iron deficiency correction is a necessary measure [14].

The studied features of the pathophysiology of iron deficiency in heart failure indicate that depletion of cellular iron reserves in HF negatively affects the maintenance of energy homeostasis of the myocardium, skeletal muscles, other organs and tissues, as well as the function of hematopoietic organs[4][15]. Iron, in addition to its key role in the absorption and transport of oxygen in hemoglobin, plays an important role in the storage and metabolism of oxygen in cells, the redox cycle, and is necessary as a cofactor of a number of enzymes that protect against reactive oxygenspecies [15]. Therefore, maintaining normal iron homeostasis is crucial for cells that require high energy uptake, such as cardiomyocytes. Iron deficiency is known to negatively affect mitochondrial function and myocardial contractility. Studies have shown that iron deficiency directly affects the function cardiomyocytes of human cardiomyocytes, disrupting mitochondrial respiration and reducing the contractility and relaxation of cardiomyocytes, while restoring the level of intracellular iron led to the opposite effect[16].

Cellular disorders resulting from iron deficiency have a clear clinical expression in the form of deterioration of functional status and an increased risk of death in patients with HF, even at normal hemoglobin levels[17]. Iron deficiency leads to the

development of sympathetic activation, left ventricular hypertrophy, dilatation of the heart chambers, and impaired central hemodynamics, which worsens the prognosis of patients with HF[18]. Thus, adverse changes in the cardiovascular system associated with iron deficiency are the main mechanisms of worsening the prognosis of life in patients with HF.

The prevalence of anemia in patients with CHF ranges from 30% to 50%, depending on the selection criteria for the study. The results suggest that older age, тяжёлаяsevere heart failure, poor nutrition, and increased inflammatory markers are associated with a higher incidence of anemia. However, the most common factor contributing to the development of anemia in HF is iron deficiency [6]. Anemia in patients with acute decompensated HF is estimated to occur more frequently in more than 50% of cases, regardless of LVEF, which is significantly higher than the prevalence in the general population (less than 10%), although the prevalence increases with age, exceeding the threshold of 20% in respondents aged ≥ 85 years [19]. The results of the studies suggest that patients with CHF who had anemia, compared with patients without anemia, were older and more often female, more often had diabetes mellitus(DM), CKD, severe HF with a worse functional status, lower exercise tolerance, lower quality of life, and more often had edema hypotension and needed higher doses of loop diuretics[19].

FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS OF IRON DEFICIENCY IN HF

Diagnosis of iron deficiency in HF presents some difficulties. The concentration of ferritin in the blood serum is a marker of the amount of iron in the depot. It is known that in the absence of inflammation or chronic disease, serum ferritin correlates with iron reserves in the body and ferritin serum ferritin of 100 mcg /l corresponds to ≈ 1 g of tissue iron. In healthy people, ferritin levels below 30 mcg /l and насыщения transferrin iron saturation index (EFI) below 16% determine iron deficiency [19].

In the development of inflammatory conditions, including HF, the level of ferritin is non-specifically elevated as an acute phase reagent, which makes identification of absolute or functional iron deficiency difficult [5]. For this reason, ferritin levels < 100

mcg/l or <300 mcg/L, if LVL <20%, have been used in various clinical trials to correct iron deficiency in patients with HF to identify patients with absolute and functional iron deficiency [13][14]. These criteria for the diagnosis of iron deficiency in patients with HF are presented in the European guidelines 2021[20],[21].

It should be remembered that the concentration of iron in the blood serum can have large daily fluctuations in patients with HF, so this laboratory indicator cannot be independently used to diagnose iron deficiency in this category of patients. However, there are other methods of diagnosing iron deficiency that are applicable in HF. For example, the level of rRTp, which increases with iron deficiency and is not affected by inflammation. It is rRTf or transferrin iron saturation (HTF) that among all diagnostic parameters have the strongest correlation with depletion of iron reserves in the bone marrow, regardless of other conditions [22].

Another important marker of iron deficiency in HF may be hepcidin, which is the main regulator of iron absorption[4]. The level of hepcidin increases in chronic diseases, including CHF, since, in addition to regulating iron absorption, it is an acute phase protein. Normally, the level of hepcidin increases with increasing iron levels, but in CHF and any inflammatory disease, hepcidin increases independently of iron levels, which leads to functional iron deficiency due to a slowdown in its absorption in the gastrointestinal tract and release from macrophages [19]. Hepcidin may become a potential target of therapy for functional iron deficiency in HF, which requires further study.

Thus, all patients with CHF, regardless of the level of hemoglobin in the blood, should be examined to assess the presence and severity of iron deficiency[11][21].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the results of numerous studies indicate that iron deficiency conditions have a significant impact on the course of CVD, are an independent predictor of the risk of adverse clinical outcomes, and therefore an early diagnosis of anemia and iron deficiency is necessary to assess the risk and conduct optimal drug correction. Over the past two decades, the prognosis and treatment approaches for patients with iron

deficiency and symptomatic CHF and LVEF <50%, acute decompensated HF and LVEF <50% have been thoroughly investigated. These studies formed the basis for the development of an algorithm for the diagnosis and treatment of iron-deficient conditions in CHF, which are presented in clinical recommendations from various countries around the world. Unfortunately, these studies were focused on patients with HF and reduced ejection fraction, and studies for patients with CHF and preserved LVEF are ongoing. Modern clinical practice is in urgent need of research that could provide a clear answer to the question of the effectiveness and safety of iron deficiency correction in patients with other CVD (AF, CHD).

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